

Promotion of Energy Conservation Techniques in Textile processing Industry: A Case Study

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Abstract:

The importance of energy conservation awareness at home is relatively easy to understand, but its thorough implementation is usually delayed in the early stages of energy conservation awareness programs in factory. Therefore, for concrete implementation, it is desirable to develop company-wide coordination measures similar to QC activities in factories. In addition, in order to promote energy-saving measures efficiently, we have identified key areas in which common Energy Savings are achieved through our Experience in Energy Auditing of about 100+ Textile Process house in South Gujarat Region.

Energy conservation is a significant step to overcoming the vital problem of the worldwide energy crisis. In particular, Sub continent countries i.e. India are interested to increase their awareness on the inefficient power generation and energy usage in their country. However, Data of energy use are limited for proper execution of energy conservation.

In developing countries energy saving and conservation technologies should be spread to all governments' organization as well as industrial owners and technocrats. It is essential that they gain practical knowledge of the presently available energy conservation technologies.

Due to high energy intensive industry i.e. textile sector; it is recommended to implements energy conservation technologies using modern energy saving techniques. For example regulating the temperature in the steam pipes, adjusting the air/fuel ratio in the boilers, and installing heat exchangers using warm waste water.

There are several ways to conserve or save energy in textile sector out of which most common suggestions in our Energy Audit will discussed in this paper.

Keywords: Energy conservation, Textile, Automation, Heat exchanger, Steam, Compressor.

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1. Introduction

1.1 Most common energy conservation in textile processing; Energy audit case studies

1.1.1 Electrical Demand Control

Increase Contract demand: From bill analysis of last year it is observed that, at present Plant is running with 78 KW contract demand. Minimum billing demand 78 kW. Plant has average Actual MD 122 kW and Maximum MD is 141 kW in Month Oct 22. Billing demand is greater than Actual demand in all month & we have to pay penalty charges in each month for excess demand charges [1]. So, we proposed to increase contract demand to 99 KW than you will save Rs. 5,565/- per Month i.e. Rs. 66,780/- per year. So increase in demand should take consideration of future requirement/expansion of plant.

Detailed calculation shown as under:

Total Saving = Rs.66,780/-
Investment = Nil
Payback Period = Immediate

1.1.2 Reduction in Contract demand

From bill analysis of last year it is observed that, at present Plant is running with 350 KVA contract demand. Minimum billing demand 298 kVA. Plant has average Actual MD 202 kVA and Maximum MD is 277 kVA in Month Dec-21 with PF of 0.974. Billing demand is greater than Actual demand in all month. So, We proposed to reduce contract demand to 300 KVA than minimum billing demand will be 255 KVA then you will save Rs.7,600/- per Month i.e. Rs. 91,200/- per year. Once you reduce demand you cannot further reduces till 1 years. So reduction in demand should take consideration of future requirement/expansion of plant. Detailed calculation shown in table 2 as under.

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Table 1 - Present and future requirement/expansion of Electrical Demand in plant

Sr. No.	Month	Actual MD	DGVC L Unit Consumption	Bill amount	Rate Rs./unit	Fixed Charges	Energy Charges	Present Additional Fix Charges above 78 KW @ 265/KW	Proposed Additional Fix Charges above 99 KW @ 265/KW	Saving
1	Aug - 22	121	52569	441306.81	8.39	21105.0	241817.4	11395.0	5830.0	5565.0
2	Sep - 22	127	55635	467143.60	8.40	22695.0	255921.0	12985.0	7420.0	5565.0
3	Oct - 22	141	54193	459760.51	8.48	26405.0	249287.8	16695.0	11130.0	5565.0
4	Nov - 22	133	48196	409542.43	8.50	24285.0	221701.6	14575.0	9010.0	5565.0
5	Dec - 22	126	52015	444188.98	8.54	22430.0	239269.0	12720.0	7155.0	5565.0
6	Jan - 23	113	49638	426905.81	8.60	18985.0	228334.8	9275.0	3710.0	5565.0
7	Feb - 23	123	50175	436586.62	8.70	21635.0	230805.0	11925.0	6360.0	5565.0
8	Mar - 23	78	29819	255898.34	8.58	9710.0	137167.4	-	-	-
9	Apr - 23	114	46962	414206.67	8.82	19250.0	216025.2	9540.0	3975.0	5565.0
10	May - 23	119	30688	283327.11	9.23	20575.0	141164.8	10865.0	5300.0	5565.0
11	Jun - 23	129	46353	419262.47	9.04	23225.0	213223.8	13515.0	7950.0	5565.0
12	Jul - 23	134	43936	411510.11	9.37	24550.0	202105.6	14840.0	9275.0	5565.0
TOTAL		***	560179	4869639	***	254850	2576823	138330	77115	61215
AVERAGE		122	46682	405803	8.69	21238	214735	12575	7010	5565
Maximum		141	55635	467144	9.37	26405	255921	16695	11130	5565
Minimum		78	29819	255898	8.39	9710	137167	9275	3710	5565

Table 2 - Actual billing and Reduction in billing demand

Sr. No.	Present C.D. 350 KVA, 85 % = 298 KVA					Proposed C.D. 280 KVA, 85 % = 238 KVA		
	Month	Actual M.D.	P.F.	Billing M.D.	Demand Charges	Billing M.D.	Demand Charges	Saving in Demand Charges
1	Apr - 21	162	0.999	298	44700.0	238	35700.0	9000
2	May - 21	158	0.999	298	44700.0	238	35700.0	9000
3	Jun - 21	89	0.998	298	44700.0	238	35700.0	9000
4	Jul - 21	182	0.999	298	44700.0	238	35700.0	9000
5	Aug - 21	171	0.997	298	44700.0	238	35700.0	9000
6	Sep - 21	182	0.996	298	44700.0	238	35700.0	9000
7	Oct - 21	267	0.955	298	44700.0	267	40050.0	4650
8	Nov - 21	274	0.960	298	44700.0	274	41100.0	3600
9	Dec - 21	277	0.974	298	44700.0	277	41550.0	3150
10	Jan - 22	246	0.997	298	44700.0	246	36900.0	7800
11	Feb - 22	209	0.999	298	44700.0	238	35700.0	9000
12	Mar - 22	202	0.999	298	44700.0	238	35700.0	9000
TOTAL		2419	***	3576	536400	2968	445200	91200
AVERAGE		202	0.989	298	44700	247	37100	7600

Total Saving = Rs. 91,200/-

Investment = Nil

Payback Period = Immediate

*Note: Once you reduce demand you cannot further reduces till 1 year.

2. Energy-efficiency improvement opportunities in electric motors

2.1. Replace Existing conventional standard motors by Energy Efficient Motors (IE3):

Energy efficient motors are the motors with design improvements specifically to increase operating efficiency

Table 3 - Effect of Existing conventional standard motors by Energy Efficient Motors

Sr. No.	M/C no	Existing				Proposed				Saving KW
		Rated KW	Measured KW	Eff	Load factor	Rated KW	Measured KW	Eff	Load factor	
1	m/c-02 Motor	1.9	1.953	81.0	1.03	1.9	1.839	86.0	0.97	0.114
2	m/c-03 Motor	1.5	1.595	80.0	1.06	1.9	1.484	86.0	0.78	0.111
3	m/c-03 Motor	1.5	1.685	80.0	1.12	1.9	1.567	86.0	0.82	0.118
4	m/c-04 Motor	1.9	2.07	81.0	1.09	2.2	1.934	86.7	0.88	0.136
5	m/c-04 Motor	1.9	2.11	81.0	1.11	2.2	1.971	86.7	0.90	0.139
6	m/c-08 Motor	1.9	2.232	81.0	1.17	2.2	2.085	86.7	0.95	0.147
7	m/c-08 Motor	1.9	2.095	81.0	1.10	2.2	1.957	86.7	0.89	0.138
8	m/c-09 Motor	1.9	2.175	81.0	1.14	2.2	2.032	86.7	0.92	0.143
9	m/c-09 Motor	1.9	2.169	81.0	1.14	2.2	2.026	86.7	0.92	0.143
10	m/c-11 Motor	1.5	2.278	80.0	1.52	2.2	2.102	86.7	0.96	0.176
Total - A		17.8	20.362			21.1	18.999			1.363
1	m/c-01 Motor	1.9	1.291	81.0	0.68	1.9	1.216	86.0	0.64	0.075
2	m/c-01 Motor	1.9	1.399	81.0	0.74	1.9	1.318	86.0	0.69	0.081
3	m/c-02 Motor	1.9	1.727	81.0	0.91	1.9	1.627	86.0	0.86	0.100
4	m/c-05 Motor	1.9	1.448	81.0	0.76	1.9	1.364	86.0	0.72	0.084
5	m/c-05 Motor	1.9	1.463	81.0	0.77	1.9	1.378	86.0	0.73	0.085
6	m/c-06 Motor	1.9	1.638	81.0	0.86	1.9	1.543	86.0	0.81	0.095
7	m/c-06 Motor	1.9	1.775	81.0	0.93	1.9	1.672	86.0	0.88	0.103
8	m/c-07 Motor	1.9	1.74	81.0	0.92	1.9	1.639	86.0	0.86	0.101
9	m/c-07 Motor	1.9	1.44	81.0	0.76	1.9	1.356	86.0	0.71	0.084
Total - B		17.1	13.921			17.1	13.112			0.809
Grand Total		34.9	34.283			38.2	32.110			2.173

Existing KW	Proposed KW	Annual savings Rs.	Investment Rs.	Payback period
34.283	32.110	1,47,984/-	2,92,000/-	24 Months

Note: 24 hrs/day, 300 days/annum and 9.46 Rs/unit are considered for the calculation purpose

[2]. Design improvements focus on reducing intrinsic motor losses. Improvements include the use of lower loss silicon steel, longer core, thicker wires, thinner laminations, smaller

air gap, use of copper instead of Aluminium bars in the rotor, superior bearings and a smaller fan etc.

3. Air Compressors

3.1. Leakage arresting in compressed air system

Table 4 - Loss and potential saving in compressed air system

Description	System Leakage	
	Comp.1 New	Comp.2 Old
Load time (T)	51	33
Unload time (t)	43	312
% Leakage	54.26	9.57
Leakage CFM	113.39	6.59
Losses in KW	16.797	1.145
Total Loss Kw	17.94	
Permissible % leakage	5%	5%
Potential saving in %age	49.26	4.57
Potential Leakage CFM	102.94	3.15
Saving potential in Kw	15.249	0.546
TOTAL Saving potential in Kw	15.80	

Note: Considering 5% Permissible Leakage

Technical Analysis:

Total Losses in KW : 15.80

Units Wastage Per Year : 85320 units @18 hours, 300 days

Financial Analysis:

Wastage that can be saved per year : Rs. 6,96,211/- @ Rs 8.16 per unit

Investment : Nil

Payback Period : Immediate

3.2. Replacement of old autoclave compressor and Hand print compressor with new compressor

From Pump-up test of compressor, it is found that specific consumption of old autoclave is 0.221 kW/CFM at 4.65 kg/cm² delivery pressure and hand print comp-01 is 0.203 kW/CFM at 6.75 kg/cm² delivery pressure. Specific consumption of both compressor is higher than standard specific consumption at current delivery pressure. New energy efficient compressor can give much lower specific consumption than current operation level [3]. We proposed to replace old compressor with new compressor.

Also, we can reduce current pressure setting of compressors. Proposed Auto clave compressor will be 3 HP Compressor with 3.3-4.5 kg/cm² delivery pressure setting and Hand printing compressor will be 10 HP Compressor with 5.0-6.2 kg/cm² pressure setting. We can remove VFD of Hand print compressor & operate compressor at 50 Hz with Star Delta Starter.

4. Energy-efficiency improvement opportunities in pumping systems

4.1. Optimize RO Plant HP Pump frequency to eliminate valve throttling

At present RO Plant HP Pump is running with 50% Discharge valve throttling. Pump motor is running through VFD with 50 Hz frequency. We have carried flow pattern analysis with respect to frequency and pressure [1]. We proposed to reduce frequency at 47 Hz Open discharge valve by 100% to eliminate valve losses.

Present power consumption of HP Pump = 11.93 kW
Proposed Power consumption of HP Pump = 10.44 kW @ 47 Hz

Annual energy saving = 1.49 X 18 hours X 300 days/annum
= 8046 units per annum

Financial Analysis:

Annual monetary saving = 8046 units X 7.58 Rs./unit
= 60,988/- Rs.

Investment = Nil

Simple payback period = Immediate

Table 5 - Technical Analysis of present and proposed condition

Comp	Present condition			Proposed Condition		Savings in kW
	CFM Generated	kW	SEC kW/CFM	SEC kW/CFM	kW	
Handprint Comp-01	32.697	6.64	0.203	0.17	5.56	1.08
Autoclave Comp	11.431	2.53	0.221	0.15	1.71	0.81
Total						1.89

Table 6 - Financial Analysis of present and proposed condition

Comp	Annual Working Hr	Savings in Unit per annum	Savings per annum Rs.	Investment Rs.	Payback period
Handprint Comp-01	2400	2589	19,622/-	1,00,000/-	61 Months
Autoclave Comp	5400	4381	33,208/-	40,000/-	14 Months
Total		6970	52,829/-	1,40,000/-	32 Months

Table 7 - Technical Analysis

Frequency Hz	Flow lps	Pressure Kg/cm ²	Power kW	% Valve opening	Remark
50	10000	14.5	11.93	50	Valve throttling Loss
45	9000	14	8.87	100	Water starvation
46	9250	14	9.58	100	Water starvation
47	9625	14.5	10.44	100	Optimum Condition
48	10000	15	11.3	100	Excess pressure

4.2. Reduce Inverter Frequency/Speed of Main motors of Jet Dyeing Machine No. 1 & 4 to avoid throttling loss across the valve.

During the Audit period, we found that the inverters are installed on Jet Dyeing M/c No. 1 & 4 but the valves of Jet Dyeing M/c No. 1 & 4 are throttled. It is proposed to reduce inverter frequency of main Motor of Jet Dyeing m/c No. 1 & 4 and keep the valves fully opened to avoid throttling loss across the valve. Technical and financial analysis is done with the assumptions that annual operating hours are 3600.

5. Energy-efficiency improvement opportunities in Fan systems

5.1 Reduce Inverter Frequency/Speed of Main motor of ID Fan to avoid throttling loss across the damper

During the Audit period, we found that the inverter is installed on Main motor of ID Fan but the damper of ID Fan is throttled. It is proposed to reduce inverter frequency of main Motor of ID Fan and keep the damper fully opened to avoid throttling loss across the damper. Technical and financial analysis is done with the assumptions that annual operating hours are 3600.

Table 8 - Effect of Inverter Frequency/Speed of Main motors of Jet Dyeing Machine

M/C No	Before implementation			After implementation			Saving in KW
	% Valve Throttle	Inverter Freq. Hz	Power KW	% Valve Throttle	Inverter Freq. Hz	Power KW	
Jet No. 1	50%	49.13	10.12	Fully Open	41.66	6.54	3.58
Jet No. 4	20%	Display Not Working	11.28	Fully Open	Display Not Working	10.02	1.26
Total			21.40			16.56	4.84

Table 9 - Technical and Financial Analysis Inverter Frequency/Speed of Main motors of Jet Dyeing Machine

Technical Analysis			Financial Analysis		
Before implementation Power Consumption in KW	After implementation Power Consumption in KW	Savings in KW	Investment Rs.	Annual Monetary Savings Rs.	Payback Period
21.40	16.56	4.84	Nil	1,24,930	Immediate

Table 10 - Effect of Inverter Frequency/Speed of Main motor of ID Fan

Thermo pack Boiler	Before implementation			After implementation			Saving in KW
	% Valve Throttle	Inverter Freq. Hz	Power KW	% Valve Throttle	Inverter Freq. Hz	Power KW	
ID Fan	50%	39.26	5.25	Fully Open	34.00	3.66	1.59

Table 11 - Technical and Financial Analysis of Inverter Frequency/Speed of Main motor of ID Fan

Technical Analysis			Financial Analysis		
Before implementation Power Consumption in KW	After implementation Power Consumption in KW	Savings in KW	Investment Rs.	Annual Monetary Savings Rs.	Payback Period
5.25	3.66	1.59	Nil	41,041	Immediate

Note: 12 hrs/day and 300 days/annum and Rs. 7.17 per unit are considered for the calculation purpose

6. Energy-efficiency improvement opportunities in steam systems

6.1. Reduce gas consumption by reduce Radiation & Convection loss in Steam boilers

Reduce Loss Due To Radiation & Convection loss:

In our thermal analysis, efficiency loss due to a radiation & natural convection is to be 2 % which can be reduce by using insulation of ceramic coating of high thermal resistance & low thermal conductivity material [4] from our thermal data external surface temperature of thermo pack shell portion & miscellaneous places of boiler. Following are the Leakage Point.

Consideration: NG flow rate: 1134 Nm³/hr , NCV of Natural Gas: 8544.249 Kcal/sm³, Yearly 8000 hrs operation, NG price: 48.70 Rs/sm³

For 20 TPH Steam Boiler

Existing boiler efficiency: 66.67%
Boiler efficiency with insulation: 68.67%

Energy Saving by Proper Insulation Control:

For 20 TPH Steam Boiler:

Table 11 - Technical and Financial Analysis

Technical Analysis		Financial Analysis		
Savings in s?? ³ /h??	Annual savings NG Units	Investment Rs.	Annual Monetary Savings Rs.	Payback Period
4.51	36080	4,25,000/-	17,57,096/-	2Months

7. Lighting

7.1 Switch off lights during day time

It is found that 42 nos. of light fittings can be switch off during day time as enough illumination is available due to North light & shutter during day time. Details are as per below mentioned table 12.

Table 12 - Effect of Switch off lights during day time

Department/Area	Total No. of Fittings	45 W LED	20 W LED
MNZ A	6	6	-
Near FD Fan Area	7	7	-
Reactor Area (10 mtr)	3	3	-
Packing ID Blower	3	3	-
Staff Canteen	9	-	9
Worker Canteen	8	-	8
MEE (12.5 mtr)	6	6	-
Total Fittings	42	25	17
Total Watts	1465	1125	340

No. of Lamps to be switched off= 42 Nos.
Total Power Consumption = 1.465 KW
For 10 hours = 14.65 KWH
= 14.65 units/per day
Annual Savings in units = 350 days X 14.65 = 5127 units
Annual Savings in Rs. = 5127 X 9.0Rs./unit = Rs. 46,143/-
Investment = --- NIL ---
Simple payback period = Immediate

7.2 Replacement of conventional Ceiling & Wall Fan by energy efficient BLDC Fan

It is proposed to replace the conventional Ceiling & Wall fan (60W&60W) by 34W& 35W Ceiling & Wall Fan by energy efficient BLDC fan respectively [5-8]. The benefits of the above said replacement will be tangible as well as intangible. The benefits are as under:

- i. Power savings up to 60%.
- ii. Remote controller

Technical Analysis

Total no. of fittings = 107 + 63 = 170
Total Power consumption (Present) = (107X 60) + (63X 60) W = 10.2 KW
Total Power consumption (Proposed) = (107X 34) + (63X 35) W = 5.843 KW
Annual energy saving = 4.357 X 10 hours X 350 days/annum = 15250 units per annum

Financial Analysis

Annual monetary saving = 15250 units X 9.0 Rs./unit = Rs. 1,37,250/-
Investment = (107 X 3400/-) + (63 X 3800/-) = Rs. 6,03,200/-
Simple payback period = 53 months
Note: Saving assuming 18 hrs/day & 300 days/year)

7.3 Replacement of conventional 36W electronic ballasts tube light by 20W LED tube light fitting:

It is proposed to replace the conventional tube light with electronic ballast 36W by 20W LED tube light fitting [6]. The benefits of the above said replacement will be tangible as well as intangible. The benefits are as under:

- a. Power savings up to 50%.
- b. No requirement of starter
- c. Long life up to 10000 hrs as compared to 5000 hrs for standard tube light
- d. High CRI of 85

Technical Analysis:

Total no. of fittings = 47
Total Power consumption (Present) = (47 X 36) W = 1.692 KW
Total Power consumption (Proposed) = (47 X 20) W = 0.94 KW
Annual energy saving = 0.752 X 18 hours X 300 days/annum = 4061 units per annum

Financial Analysis:

Annual monetary saving = 4061 units X 8.16 Rs./unit
 = 33,138/- Rs.
 Investment = (47 X 250/-)
 = 11,750/- Rs.
 Simple payback period = 4 months
 Note: Saving assuming 18 hrs/day & 300 days/year

5. Conclusions

This article provides information on energy-efficiency technologies and measures applicable to the textile industry. At all times, the reader must bear in mind that the values presented in this article are offered as guidelines. Actual cost and energy savings for the measures will vary, depending on plant configuration and size, plant location, plant operating characteristics, production and product characteristics, the local supply of raw materials and energy, and several other factors. For instance, for some of the energy-efficiency measures, the significant portion of the cost is the labour cost. Thus, the cost of these measures in the developed and developing may vary significantly. Therefore, for all energy-efficiency measures presented in this article, individual plants should pursue further research on the economics of the measures, as well as on the applicability of different measures to their own unique production practices, in order to assess the feasibility of measure implementation.

6. Summary of Last Five Years Energy Audit Study in Textile Processing

	Saving Identified in KWh/yr	Accumulative CO2 emissions reduction Kgs	Accumulative tree planting
TOTAL 52 Industries	20411554	17349821	103891

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